

Turn taking patterns, repair and adjacency pairs in an online interaction: a conversation analysis

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ABSTRACT

The present study analyzed the use of conversation analysis (CA) in online interaction. The aim of the study is to describe the patterns of turn taking, repair, and the adjacency pairs in the online conversation. Employing a qualitative research methodology, data were taken from an online conversation about how to learn English, taking place in YouTube between a professor of English language teaching and the host who is a professor of education. The conversation was mainly in Bahasa Indonesia. The data were first transcribed in Bahasa Indonesia and translated into English. The study found some structures of exchange in the communication and the patterns of turn taking, repairs and adjacency pairs evident from the analysis of conversation. There are some patterns of turn-taking and adjacency pairs along the online conversation. The turn constructional units vary in syntactical forms. In addition, both self-initiated and other initiated-self repairs occurred. The study drew the implication of CA to language teaching. CA contributes to language teaching in terms of offering not only the authentic real-life communication, but also the authentic spoken interaction which will encourage learners to be able to produce authentic utterances.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, regarding the development of technology, the number of learners accessing online learning resources is increasing. They are now more accustomed to online learning. This also happened in language learning including English. Apart from official or common learning management systems, students often directly access online learning resources, where they can get lessons from the experts. That is one of the learning environments as a recent form of social interaction.

Learning a language is not only learning the subject matter. It also deals with learning the strategies to help reach the best achievement in learning. This can be learned theoretically from references or directly from experts, teachers or more experienced learners. Supporting this idea educational channels intend to deliver learning information to the viewers. They offer materials in such a way that the viewers can get lessons online. They have what is called conversation, online conversation. Conversation is not restricted to casual and informal talk, but it also includes all forms of talk in interaction [1], [2]. Similar to offline interaction, an online one supports interactive social relationships between the participants but it is mediated by the internet. It can be asynchronous or synchronous [3], [4]. The recent study focuses on spoken conversation through the internet where two participants interacted in a synchronous conversation broadcast via YouTube; while earlier studies

investigated chatting online comparing spoken and written interaction [5] the one focusing second language (L2) learners' satisfaction in a synchronous online learning environment [6], stories [7], communication and language use in social media [8], [9] and in association with community [10]–[12].

Conversation analysis (CA) is used to examine the spoken interaction between the participants [1], [2], [11]. CA does not consider any other factors outside the spoken data. The researchers concern more on how the talk worked, how it interconnected, and how exchanges occurred. Talk in terms of communion of reciprocally sustained involvement [12], [13] happened through fragments of the talk. According to Schegloff *et al.* [1], [14], [15] the participants in terms of turn-taking systems, sequence organization, turn design and repair. The turn-taking system provides a structured framework allowing speakers to coordinate who speaks and when. This system operates under a set of locally managed rules that help avoid chaos in speech and ensure a fluid exchange of turns. Sequence organization further refines this interaction by dictating the order and dependency of conversational turns. Thus, it organizes the flow of conversation into coherent and predictable patterns. Meanwhile, turn design, another critical aspect, involves how speakers craft their turns to achieve specific communicative goals and adapt their speech to the context, audience, and preceding talk. Speakers choose their words, syntax, and speech tempo thoughtfully to fit into the ongoing interaction, which often requires on-the-fly adjustments. Lastly, the mechanism of repair addresses problems in speaking, hearing, or understanding that occur within the conversation. Repair can be initiated by the speaker themselves (self-repair) or by their interlocutor (other-repair), and serves to maintain mutual understanding and keep the dialogue progressing smoothly. However, the researchers limit on the turn-taking, turn design and repair. The implication of CA to language teaching is also discussed.

Some relevant studies have been conducted on online conversation using conversation analysis. Sari [16] studied the interaction of students and a teacher and found that teacher and students-turn is asymmetrical. However, the teacher possessed no absolute power in term of controlling the turn taking as students appeared to overlap the teacher's talk to take the turn and try to perform unfocalized effort to nominate themselves as the first speaker using gestures. Similarly, in the online setting, the study by Earnshaw [17] showed several different approaches to smooth speaker hand-offs. In cases where handoffs were not smooth, participants attempted corrections by either fixing the problem or by moving on. Some other studies also concern with turn taking and classroom settings [18], [19].

As one of the observed aspects of CA, turn taking is associated with how the speaker turns to avoid overlaps and communication gaps [20], [21]. In talk, a series of turn taking reflects patterns that develop sequence organization. The structure is reflected in adjacency pairs. It is an automatic pattern of utterances produced by different speakers spoken by the second speaker associated with the first speaker and expected to follow what initiated and uttered by the first speaker. When it does not happen, repair may emerge as a response to the speaker. Turn taking, repair and adjacency pairs develop the fragments of the conversation. Through this study, the researchers reveal the patterns of the turn taking, repair, and adjacency pairs in the online conversation discussing how to learn English easily.

2. METHOD

The data of this qualitative study were collected from two participants in an online conversation talking about how to learn English easily [22]. The first is an ELT expert and the second is an online video channel host who is a professor in education. Both the speaker and the host work at the same university. The host introduced himself by mentioning his YouTube channel using his name. For the audience, he introduced the speaker in her complete name, title, expertise and affiliation. Pseudo names are used. Culturally, both are Javanese. They talked in Indonesian. They address using *Pak* (Sir) or *Bu* (Ma'am). Some English and Javanese expressions were heard in some parts of their conversation. The participants (the speaker and the host) discussed how to learn English easily. Therefore, it is a goal-directed. The total duration of the video is 33:11 minutes. The data were transcribed into Indonesian. Translation into English by the researchers was conducted to facilitate dissemination to the academic public. Analysis was conducted by capturing the interactions recorded between the speaker and the host during the online interaction [5], talking about learning English. It is to reveal how the turn taking, repair and adjacency pairs occurred. This is to find out what sequence of activities during the conversation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents three chores in conversation analysis. They are turn taking, repair and adjacency pairs. Those three aspects are important parts in the conversation analysis. They develop the conversation between the participants. Sometimes, turn taking and repair happens at the same time during the conversation.

3.1. Turn taking

The data shows that the patterns of turn taking and repair emerged in different forms. As commonly happens in a conversation, participants exchange their role as a speaker and hearer [23], [24]. The turn constructional units (TSUs) appear in different forms of syntax as shown in Table 1. They are in the form of words, phrase, and clause. forming a recognizable complete utterance.

Table 1. Syntactic forms of turn constructional unit

TSU	Examples	Translation	Line
Clausal	Anto: <i>Assalamualaikum warahmatullahi wabarakatuh, Bu. Asih.</i>	<i>Assalamualaikum warahmatullahi wabarakatuh</i> (Peace be upon you and God's mercy and blessings), Mrs Asih	1
	Asih: <i>Waalaiikumsalam warahmatullahi wabarakatuh. Pak Anto apa kabar?</i>	<i>Waalaiikumsalam warahmatullahi wabarakatuh</i> (And peace be upon you and God's mercy and blessings), Mr. Anto how are you?	2
	Anto: <i>Alhamdulillah baik Bu...Dan kali ini akan kita mulai dengan bagaimana mengetahui keunikan kata kerja.</i>	<i>Alhamdulillah</i> , fine Ma'am... And now we 'll start with how to understand the uniqueness of the verb.	3
	Asih: <i>Ya saya kira itu penting Pak...</i>	Yes, I think that is important, Sir.	4
Phrasal	Anto: <i>Kalau anu Bu, kalau orang bisa kuliah di negara native, yang nativenya Inggris itu berapa? 10 ribu bisa?</i>	If ...err..Ma'am, if one can study abroad in an English speaking country, how should the vocabulary level to be prepared? 10 thousand, is ok?	36
	Asih: <i>E...delapan ribu ke atas.</i>	e...more than eight thousand	37
	Anto: <i>O, delapan ribu ke atas.</i>	O...more than eight thousand	38
	Asih: <i>Itu..itu...Kalau lebih jelas ya, lebih. Dulu dikiranya itu hanya empat ribu cukup. (tertawa) Ternyata kan tidak cukup, Pak Anto.</i>	E...more is better, yes, more. It used to be only four thousand words (laughs) It turned out that it wasn't enough, Mr. Anto.	39

In the conversation, clause or sentences (lines 1–4) are also used by the host (named Anto) and the speaker (named Asih) during turn taking as shown in Table 1. In other parts of the online interaction, they expressed their ideas in phrases (lines 37, 38). They indicate how speakers format their turns to implement some actions, in some position [25].

Further, the clauses or sentences the host used are declarative (line 8), interrogative (line 62), and imperative (line 154). For example,

- Asih (L6) : *Kemudian nirokke itu berarti mengulangi sambil ini, nambahin baru* (Then 'nirokke'- Javanese word- means repeating while adding new ones).
- Anto (L7) : *Wah ini ajaran Ki Hajar ini ya?* (Wow, this is Ki Hajar's teaching, isn't it?)
- Asih (L8) : *Betul, Saya share dulu ya. Jadi modal kita memang kalau bahasa itu telaten, kemudian teliti, dan niteni, tapi juga harus mengulangi dan mengulangi* (Correct, I'll share this first. Indeed, in learning a language we have to be *telaten* or painstaking, then *teliti* or thorough, and *niteni* or meticulous, then we also have to repeat and repeat).
- Anto (L6) : *Ini, ini memahami ini gimana Bu? Ada pilihan atau sesuka-suka atau hirarkikal itu?* (This, how did you understand this, Ma'am? Is there any choice, free or hierarchical?)
- Asih (L63) : *Ada. A.., kalau hirarkinya itu, hirarki karena frekuensi tadi ya Pak* (Sure. Arr, for that hierarchy, the hierarchy is because of the frequency, Sir.)
- Anto (L154) : *Ya, satu slide lagi Bu, lima menit* (Ok, one more slide, Ma'am, five minutes)
- Asih (L155) : *Ok. Nah ini hanya ini...yang tadi itu. I will do my homework as soon as possible. Well, you can do better than that. (Ok, this is it..the one we talked about. I will do my homework as soon as possible. Well, you can do better than that)*

Regarding the turn constructional unit in the form of words, it is concealed that the use of 'ya (yes)' showing agreement is in the big number. The host is often in accordance with what the speaker stated. It is identified that there are one hundred and two (102) 'ya' utterances the whole duration of the online session which lasted in 33:11 minutes. Similarly, the host also used the words such as 'betul' (correct), and ok for his confirmation to the speaker's utterances. In Javanese culture, people tend to be in harmony, that' is why during the conversation both participants often used "ya" both when expressing agreement or stimulating others to agree.

From the data obtained, it is proved that TSUs vary in the form of words, phrases and clauses or sentences. It is also reasonable that the length of turn also varies, not fixed considering the dynamics in having conversation comprising turn taking, sequential organizing of turns and contexts when the conversation is taking place [26]. When the speaker is explaining, the host seemed waiting for longer time to take his role. In

fact, he did not speak much because he only gave necessary often short comments to respond to the speaker, mostly in agreement. The longest time when he played his role was in the beginning of the conversation which took almost 2 minutes. It is when he led the viewers to the program and to introduce the speaker.

3.2. Repair

Repair then happens when in some of the conversation fragments, the speaker found something she disagreed and she thought it is needed to make correction. The host is not always in line with the speaker, and vice versa. Each in some fragments shows their agreement or disagreement. Repair practices address troubles in the conversation. It includes trouble source, repair initiation, and repair solution. It can be self-initiated self-repair or other-initiated self-repair. These two repairs exist in the conversation in this study.

That was when the host talked about looking up the meaning of an idiom in a dictionary and the speaker clarified about the presence of idioms in the dictionary.

- Anto (L208) : *Padahal idiom itu kan? nggak selalu bisa dilihat di kamus* (In fact? sometimes idioms can be checked in the dictionary).
- Asih (L209) : *(ehm). Ada Pak? Kalau yang kamus gede Pak? janganlah kamus kecil* (ehm, the idioms are there, Sir? in the dictionary, a thick or big one, Sir, no? a pocket dictionary).
- Anto (L212) : *Yang Webster atau apa gitu?* (Webster dictionary or what?).
- Asih (L213) : *Enggak, yang ini aja ada? Webster terlalu besar ya. Yang Cambridge seperti ini. Kalau ini ya saya punya yang sak meja, sak gini itu, ini banget. Jadi memang telaten* (No, just this one? Webster is too big. Such a Cambridge is ok. I have one, the table dictionary, very big. So, the students must be taking their perseverance in using the dictionary).

However, following the discussion, it was revealed that in lines 220 and 222, the host reminded the speaker to repair the mistype because it was part of documenting correct information for the learners.

- Anto (L220) : *Anu Bu, ini bisa diedit nggak offline nya ini* (.Hmm, can this part of slide be edited later in the offline version?).
- Anto (L222) : *Karena ini kan terdokumentasi masalahnya* (Because this recording is for the documentation).

In the conversation in this study, the self-repair also appeared when the speaker was aware of having mistype and she intended to revise it later (Line 225). In this case, turn taking and repair are at the same time during the conversation. Since it is the conversation in the video that the researchers used, the turn taking is also seen from the visual. This happened when the speaker was responding to the host, she took her turn and asked the house to wait because she intended to move to a slide of which mistype needed to be revised ---line 225. What the speaker means is the idiom of, not the idiom if.

- Asih (L225) : *Sebentar, Pak. Betul, itu memang tadi o-i dan o-u, kan jejeran, Pak? Jaraknya dekat. Itu kalau orang bahasa Inggris kan malah justru untuk menguji kemampuan berpikir kontekstual (Pak Anto tertawa)* (Wait, Sir. Ok, that was o-i and o-u, these letters are in the same line on keyboard, aren't they? Closed one another. For English learners, that can be testing to think contextually. (Mr. Anto was laughing)).

Similar to turn taking, repair can be in different syntactical forms. The excerpt from the above-mentioned line 209 shows that the expression of repair is represented by a sentence, a simple sentence. Whereas, the excerpt from line 213 is not necessarily a sentence, it can be a phrase then it was followed by some other sentences. In the conversation, the speaker and the host back and forth exchange information, messages. Sometimes one is supporting the other by agreeing or confirming. Some other time they have their own stance. These activities construct the strings of utterances in the conversation to become organized activities between conversation participants. The organized activities between the first pair part (FPP) and the second pair part (SPP) are called conditional relevance [14]. The conditional relevance is often represented by adjacency pair, one of the components in conversation to be paid attention to.

3.3. Adjacency pairs

In an adjacency pair, the second speaker's utterances depend on the first speaker's [27], [28]. The adjacency pair sets up a transition relevance and expectation which the next speaker fulfilled [26], [28], [29]. In this study, it is found out that there are several forms of adjacency pairs in the online conversation on ELT. They are in the form of greeting-greeting, question-answer, statement-explanation, statement confirmation including the host's short expressions to respond to the speaker positively.

In the beginning of the conversation, an adjacency pair is present. As both participants are Muslims, they exchanged greeting in Muslim greeting in Arabic. “*Assalaamu ‘alaikum warahmatullahi wabarakatuh*” was used, and it was replied in the same language (*Wa ‘alaikumsalam warahmatullahi wabarakatuh*) accordingly (lines 1, 2, and the last lines 232, 233). The greeting means “peace be upon you and God’s mercy and blessings be upon you as well”. This is the complete utterances of giving and replying salaam or greeting in Islam. In shorter expressions, the greetings can be *salaam*, *assalamu ‘alaikum*, or *assalamu ‘alaikum warahmatullah*. Such greetings are also a prayer (*du’a*) that demands Muslims to reply. It is a good deed and part of a Muslim’s obligation according to Imam Nawawi [30], [31].

Another adjacency pair is found in question-answer. This is very common to happen in a conversation. Co-occurrence of questions and answers as a socially normative organization. Question and answer so that they build relevant parts of the conversation. The question receives two responses: one answering the question in the negative and one assessing the object in question.

However, based on the data obtained, there is a very limited number of this question answer adjacency pair. There are ‘only’ four adjacency pairs of question and answer: line 2 when the host asked how the speaker is, line 36 when asking about the vocabulary mastery to study abroad (“*how should the vocabulary level to be prepared? 10 thousand is ok?*”), line 62 (“*This, how did you understand this, Ma’am? Is there any choice, free or hierarchical?*”) and 178 on idioms (“*Is it do sport or do exercise?*”).

It is the fact that the host in this study rarely raised explicit questions. He often invited the speaker to share her knowledge, skills and experiences by uttering stimulating statements. To start a conversation leading to rich information, the host said, “*And now we ‘ll start with how to understand the uniqueness of the verb.*” ---line 3. Another example is “*That was good, the same as “do harm.”*” ---line 174.

In most of the conversation under the study, the host made statement confirmations, to be more precise in different syntactical forms. Mostly the host used expressions of agreement to the speaker’s thoughts therefore he often said “*ya, ok, betul*” – yes, ok, right) whether or not he was asked to share his. The massive use of “*ya, ok, betul* and such expressions” increased in frequency while both participants used question tags which have various forms like “*isn’t it? ok*”. It was evident that the host often uses his short expression “*ya, ya,*” to show his agreement to the speaker. He used that expression 102 times on the 33 minutes of show duration. For example,

- L 29: And then sometimes there are words that are rarely encountered. It seems that they are only present in some texts.
- L 30: Ok, that is low frequency. If it is low, it cannot be used in some places, in certain texts. Those verbs often used are in certain texts, therefore. on the contrary there are verbs often, they are called high frequency. ...---line 31. Some other examples are
- L 22: *Nah kalau kita mengapa saya katakan bentuk tertulisnya dulu. Karena kebanyakan kita ini kan bukan apa namanya, mendengarkan dulu ya. Lihat tulisannya dulu ya.* (So, why did I say the written form first? Because most of us learn through writing first, not listening first, don’t we?)
Ya (Yes)
- L 24: *Tulisannya dulu. Baru nanti lafalnya gitu lho. Itu penting. Dua itu. Nah baru setelah itu bagaimana sih perilakunya di dalam kalimat, perilaku ini. Jadi kita katakan behavior ya.* (Writing first, then pronunciation, that’s it. That’s important, both of them. Those two. So, after that, how is the behavior in the sentence?)
Atau apa, Semua orang yang ingin belajar bahasa itu harus telaten. (Everyone who wants to learn the language must be persevering)
Ya betul, sama Bu, yang belajar harus telaten, yang ngajar juga nggak boleh sebel.
(Yes, I agree Ma’am, the learners must have perseverance and the teacher must do, too when teaching)

3.4. Discussion

There is a variety of interactional roles the participants occupy considering the dynamic during the online conversation. Because there is a goal of delivering information on how to learn English easily as a foreign language, the ELT professor is mostly as the speaker and the host of the program as the recipient. However, in some fragments of the conversation, they take different roles such as speaker of trouble source and repair initiator (lines 28, 29; lines 208, 209).

Regarding the turn taking, the participants contribute each other to what is getting done. They function turn construction units in different syntactical forms: lexical, phrasal and clausal. Considering the duration of the sessions (33 minutes 11 seconds), the program host seems to limit his roles by using simple and short expressions very often to confirm the speaker’s utterances. The host as the recipient did not raise many explicit questions, he triggered the ideas leading to the discussion on how to learn English easily. He involved his personal and academic experiences, and so did the speaker. The conversation engaged both participants since they had things in common, such as organizational, academic, cultural, professorship background. Such can be applied in an English teaching

and learning process. A teacher may take his/her role as a facilitator, manager, prompter, and motivator, a teacher is not always as a resource or assessor or evaluator [32]. It is to encourage the students to be actively expressing their ideas, feelings and experiences. When sharing, they use an easy, motivating and insightful words, this is as presented by the speaker and the host in the online interaction.

It is resulted on how the participants felt comfortable in taking initiatives to take lead to any thread of conversation discussing the topic in question, starting from greetings, asking question, confirming answers, etc. This hopefully applies in teaching and learning English as a foreign language. Students' attention to what was delivered by the teacher or lecturer as one of the learning sources and their critical thinking are to be stimulated and accommodated so that dialogues and discussion can be manifested like what the host and the speaker presented during the conversation. Also, when each of them gave feedbacks or commented the other participant's idea by using different languages (Javanese, Arabic, Indonesian, English), the organization of actions ran smoothly until the end of the fragment. It supports the idea that turn initial particles can project the type of action that incipient turn will implement [25]. In non-native English-speaking countries, multilingualism is inevitable. It enhances cognitive flexibility, enabling learners to switch between languages and perspectives more adeptly. It broadens cultural awareness and sensitivity, providing students with deeper insights into different societies and ways of thinking. Additionally, multilingual students often display improved problem-solving skills, as they are accustomed to processing information and expressing ideas in various linguistic frameworks [33], [34].

Affective particles such as how they addressed each other which show respect as well as engagement as professional academicians and counterparts (use of "Professor" and "*Pak, Bu* and nicknames"). This is evident when they referred to their past mentioning one of their colleagues who was good in English, or their experiences in teaching and learning to encourage the viewers to learn English. The speaker in the beginning after greeting, stated that in learning English, she noticed, took examples, repeated, modified the materials. Supported by her perseverance, she was successful being a professor of English education with her great work and achievements.

In addition, prosodic accents and intonational contours of the turn taking are more manifested when the participants found some utterances to repair. The speaker's intonation sounds raising (the above-mentioned line 208, 209, lines 212, 213). Short utterances such as "*ya, ya, ok*" implied that the participant-the host, provides the speaker a moment to share her stance, to explain further her ideas related to English teaching and learning.

Conversation provides authentic materials for language learning [35]. Language learning including English language learning is now supported by the development of technology. Delivering a lesson through online conversation exposes the learners to get rich materials related to macro and micro levels of discourse as stated by Cots *et al.* [34], and Riggenbach [36], at which learners can obtain information on power, value systems, prestige and status as well as on the prosody like falling or rising intonation, stressed or unstressed syllabus. It is undeniable that through online conversation, learners can also grab grammatical structures from the participants in the conversation.

4. CONCLUSION

The online interaction in the form of spoken synchronous conversation through the internet on how to learn English easily provides rich spoken language phenomena. It presents some patterns of turn taking, repair, and the adjacency pairs in the conversation. The online session facilitates the observation of how learners manage conversation flow and negotiate meaning in real-time. Moreover, the immediacy of spoken interactions online between the host and the speaker allows for instant feedback and clarification, enhancing not only how to deal with interaction and communication but also what teaching and learning material is obtained from the conversation. Additionally, exposure to varied accents and dialects in such settings enriches the learners' language skills and linguistic adaptability. This dynamic setup also encourages the use of informal language and idioms, crucial for achieving fluency. The roles of the participants, the utterances used along the online conversation are great contributions to be considered in the practice of teaching and learning English as a foreign language.

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